

UNIVERSITAT POMPEU FABRA

MASTER THESIS PROJECT

**Discovery of Percussion Patterns
from Tabla Solo Recordings**

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Abstract

This thesis aims to explore the problem of percussion pattern discovery in Indian art music specific to Hindustani music. We propose approaches for automatic discovery of percussion patterns from audio recordings of tabla solos. We take advantage of the onomatopoeic syllables used in transmission of the repertoire and the technique. We provide a short introduction to the concept of rhythm in Hindustani music, explaining the essential components that constitute a rhythmic cycle. We review the relevant research for transcription and pattern search in music using computational methods and present a critique. A detailed description and the implementation steps for the proposed methods are presented. In our approach, the recordings of the Tabla solos are transcribed into a sequence of syllables using an HMM model of each syllable. We compile a set of most frequently occurring patterns in the dataset and use them as query patterns to be searched over the transcribed sequence of syllables. For the purpose of pattern search, we use an approximate string search method of matching Rough Longest Common Subsequence (RLCS) which, empirically, seems to be robust to the transcription errors and improves the recall rate and the f-measure significantly over the baseline. Further, we hypothesize to aid the RLCS approach by introducing syllabic similarity and non-linear costs for insertions and deletions in transcription. While the introduction of syllabic similarities gives a boost to the recall rate at the cost of precision, non-linear cost for insertions and deletions improves the precision at the cost of recall. The methods are evaluated over a sizeable dataset that has been compiled as a part of the CompMusic project. The obtained results provide a proof for the proposed concept. A detailed error analysis is performed and plausible reasons are discussed to explain the obtained results. The thesis concludes with a summary of the work, highlighting the main conclusions and the contributions made.

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Contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	The Instrument	7
1.2	Concept of Rhythm and Patterns in Tabla	10
1.3	Motivation and Hypothesis	12
2	State of the Art	14
2.1	Stroke Level Transcription	14
2.2	Pattern Search	16
2.3	Timbral Similarity	22
3	Methodology	25
3.1	Dataset	27
3.2	Preliminary Experiments	28
3.3	Transcription	30
3.4	Query Patterns	32
3.5	Error Analysis on Transcribed Data	33
3.6	Pattern Search on Symbolic Data	37
3.6.1	Variants of RLCS	39
3.6.2	Timbral Distance	41
4	Experiments and Results	43
4.1	Transcription	43
4.2	Pattern Search	45
5	Summary and Future Work	50
5.1	Summary of work	50
5.2	Conclusions	51
5.3	Open issues and Future work	51
5.4	Main Contributions	53

List of Figures

1.1	Parts of instrument	7
1.2	Teental Theka	10
3.1	Overall Block Diagram	27
3.2	Frames per syllables	29
3.3	Log Likelihoods of frames by bōl models	30
3.4	Self Similarity matrix for frames represented by log likelihoods of of syllable models	31
3.5	Distribution of length of true positive and false negative syllable sequences for DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA	34
3.6	Distribution of length of true positive and false negative syllable sequences for TA, TA, KI, TA	34
3.7	Block Diagram for the RLCS approach	37
3.8	Function for non-linear cost of insertion and deletions	40
3.9	Self-similarity plot of syllable timbres	42
4.1	Ground truth self similarity in score space	44
4.2	Transcribed score self similarity in score space	44
4.3	Effect of variation of β	46
4.4	Distribution of length of true positive and false positive syllable sequences for DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA	47
4.5	Distribution of length of true positive and false positive syllable sequences for TA, TA, KI, TA	47

List of Tables

3.1	Timbrally grouped syllables of tabla	25
3.2	Statistically obtained query patterns	32
3.3	Transcribed sequences at positions of DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA .	35
3.4	Transcribed sequences at positions of TA, TA, KI, TA	35
3.5	Transcribed sequences at positions of KI, TA, TA, KI	36
4.1	Results for automatic transcription	43
4.2	RLCS variants and their performance	45
4.3	Results segregated for each pattern	48

Chapter 1

Introduction

Percussion instruments have always been an essential part in Indian art music. *Tabla*, in Hindustani music, and *Mridangam*, in Carnatic music, are the main rhythm accompanying instruments. *Tabla* has been widely used in both Hindustani classical and semi-classical music. It has also gained popularity amongst the community of musicians who create fusion music. This can be attributed to the timbral richness of the instrument. Apart from being an accompanying instrument, the richness of its timbre has enabled tabla artists to showcase solo performance. With its increasing popularity over different geographical areas, it is important to formulate and attempt to solve research problems associated to it that could help in striding forward the knowledge of the MIR community. It is also important to formulate research problems that are culturally relevant. Most of the cultural specific research for percussion instruments in Indian art music is centered around automatic transcription of syllables. On the other hand the research on percussions in the western music has been dealing with problems of percussion and rhythmic patterns.

This thesis is an attempt to take a step forward in case of Indian art music as well and try to formulate and devise a possible solution for discovery of percussion patterns in case of Indian art music specifically dealing with tabla and Hindustani music. We first describe the instrument tabla followed by an explanation of the concepts of rhythm in Hindustani music. Forming a theoretical base, we then try to explain our motivation behind the problem we are trying to solve and present a hypothesis. We then do a review of the relevant work underlining the importance of the problem we are trying to attempt.

Figure 1.1: The instrument and its parts¹.

1.1 The Instrument

Tabla consists of two drums. Various names are given to each part of the instrument depending on region of India and the language spoken there. As there are fifteen main languages spoken in India with hundred of dialects, there are variations in names and their pronunciations. The measurement of the instruments are usually expressed in inches, like 1, $1\frac{1}{4}$, $1\frac{1}{2}$, $1\frac{3}{4}$, 2, $2\frac{1}{4}$, etc., although the metric system is also in use. It should be noted that no matter which system is used, the measurements do somewhat vary. We will now describe the different parts of the instruments. Figure 1.1 shows an image of the instrument mentioning its parts [4, p. 69].

Dāyān (Tabla, Siddha, Dahina, Lakari)

The word ‘*dāyān*’ literally means ‘right’ and it is used to name the right drum for a right-handed person. The *dāyān* has a high pitch and is capable of producing several harmonic overtones unique to Indian drums. It is possible to produce around five tonal pitches on the drumhead with each one having a few overtones. The *dāyān* is approximately 14 cm in diameter at the opening and around 27 cm in height, which can vary as there are many sizes and shapes of the shell. The shell is usually made of *śiśama* (teak) or some other type of heavy wood. The *dāyān* is tuned to a fixed note in a composition which is the tonic set for a

¹<https://divyamsethi.files.wordpress.com/2014/09/tabla.jpg>

particular composition during the performance [4, p. 69].

Bāyān (Digga, Duggi, Dhama, Pital, Tamba)

The word ‘*bāyān*’ literally means ‘left’ and it is used to name the left drum for a right-hand person. The deep sound of the *bāyān* represents the heart of the instrument and it literally ‘speaks’ by using a constant modulation of tonal frequency known as *gamak*. These modulations are achieved by moving back of the left wrist after the membrane is struck. The *bāyān* has a lower pitch than the *dāyān* and it is tuned according to the composition in various manners. The membrane of the *bāyān* usually measures about 24 cm in diameter at the opening and the height of the shell is approximately 27 cm. The shape and sounds can vary according to the desired characteristics of the sound [4, p. 70].

Purī (Puddi, Palli)

Purī is used to name the circle-shaped bread which is part of Indian cuisine and it demarcates the tabla membrane. The *purī* is made of several parts and considering the playing techniques, the important ones are: *syahi*, *maidān*, *chanti*, *gajarā* (shown in Figure 1.1). We now describe each of these in short to know their roles:

- **Syahi:** The word *syahi* is derived from the word ‘*siyah*’ which means black. *Syahi* is a black spot in the center of the *purī* and it is made of a few layers of special paste which consists of whole wheat flour, white wheat flour, iron powder, special stone powder and glue or starch. The *syahi* largely influences the musical pitch of tabla as a thicker *syahi* creates a lower pitch while a thinner *syahi* makes it higher. On *dāyān*, the *syahi* is usually about 6 – 7 cm in diameter while on the *bāyān*, it is about 8 – 9 cm [4, p. 70].
- **Maidān:** *Maidān* is the base membrane of the tabla *purī*. It is made of the finest and thinnest processed goat skin [4, p. 71].
- **Chanti:** The term *chanti* means ‘corner’ and it is the ring of skin on the edge of the *purī*. This is also made from the goat skin but is a little thicker than the leather used for *maidān*. Its function is to moderate harmonic overtones and acts as the base for producing different sounds of the drum [4, p. 71].
- **Gajarā:** A *gajarā* is made of a thick, strong Indian water buffalo hide and it is weaved to form the rim of the *purī* through which *baddhi* (1.1) is

weaved afterwards. Its function is to connect all the layers of the membrane to the wooden shell with baddhi braces which pass through it and set the tonal pitch of the membrane [4, p. 71].

There are many other parts of the instrument as well (1.1). But, we keep ourselves limited to the description of the above mentioned parts as they are the primary parts responsible for the timbral nature of tabla.

Onomatopoeic Syllables

Many music traditions around the world have developed systems for oral mnemonic syllables for transmission of the repertoire and technique [43], one of which is Indian art music. Traditionally, rhythm in Indian music was not written down but transferred orally from generation to generation [4, p. 120]. Playing tabla is taught and learned through the use of onomatopoeic oral mnemonic syllables called the *bōls*, which are vocal syllables corresponding to different timbres that can be produced on a tabla. Though the primary function of these *bōls* is to provide a representation system, a rhythmic vocal recitation of the *bōls*, which requires high skills, is inserted into solo performances for music appreciation. Since, the *bōls* are mnemonics for the strokes, a student devotes considerable amount of time in reciting the sequence of *bōls* of a composition. This helps in understanding the aesthetics of a particular composition. Though traditionally, the *bōls* were not written down, recently rhythm is written down by using various scripts of the Indian subcontinent like Devanagari solely for the purpose of noting down the *bōls* for a composition. This practice is very prominent in the university like setup since they have fixed syllabus approach. Some other scripts such as Latin ad Roman have also been put into use for the same purpose. Roman has been put into a lot of use recently mainly for the purpose of representing the concepts in English books as well as electronically. The system of rhythmic notation is called ‘*tāl lipī*’.

Since, several *bōls* correspond to same timbre played on the tabla, creating a many *bōl* to same timbre mapping, which can be exploited to make the process of automatic transcription less challenging. This can further be exploited for the purpose of pattern search and discovery type of problems. The *bōls* of the tabla are classified into the following classes [4, p. 144]:

- *Bōls* played on the *dāyān*
- *Bōls* played on the *bāyān*
- *Bōls* played in unison

- Bōls played as a flam
- Bōls played in a quick succession

In the above list, *flam* are the combination of bōls, played in a manner that one bōl immediately follows the other. Also, the bōls that are played as a flam or in a successive manner can be segmented into the first three categories. Hence, we define all the bōls in our set as strokes belonging to any of the first three categories as mentioned above (i.e. played on dāyān, played on the bāyān or played in unison).

1.2 Concept of Rhythm and Patterns in Tabla

The structure of rhythm in India is completely different from those found in Middle East or the classical music that took shape in medieval Europe. These systems use rhythmic sequences divided into bars and the structure of the rhythm appears more like a group of small sequences rather than unified and compact rhythmic cycles [4, p. 119]. In Indian art music, rhythm has compactness and a flowing feeling of a cycle determined by a unique breathe-in-breathe-out feeling formed by ascent and descent points known as *tālī* and *khalī* that give a unique breathing pulsation [4, p. 120].

To demonstrate the concept tālī and khalī, the most basic rhythm in Hindustani music ‘Teen Taal Theka’ would be the best example:

X					2				
DHA	DHIN	DHIN	DHA	DHA	DHIN	DHIN	DHA		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
0					3				
DHA	TIN	TIN	TAA	TAA	DHIN	DHIN	DHA		
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16		

Figure 1.2: Tāl lipi representation of Teental Theka

Figure 1.2 shows the 16 *mātrās* or beats in the rhythmic cycle. The rhythm has four different sequences called *vibhāgs* or ‘sections’, which are close to what a measure would mean in the western nomenclature and are divided by the vertical lines in Figure 1.2. The rhythm cycle generally consists of two portions, one which represents the breathe-in (from beats 1-8 in figure 1.2) and another breathe-out (from beats 9-16 in Figure 1.2). Together these portions form a unique breathing feeling, which is the major characteristic of Indian rhythm.

Each *vibhāg* starts with variously emphasized points:

- *Sam*, meaning ‘join together’ is the point that is on *mātrā* (beat) 1 in Figure 1.2 and is marked as ‘X’. This is analogous to the downbeat and the beginning of a *tāl* cycle.
- *Tālī*, meaning ‘clap’ is an accented point but less than the *sam*. They are represented by number in order starting from 2 (since the first one is the *sam*). In Figure 1.2 we see this on *mātrā* 5 and 13 marked as ‘2’ and ‘3’ respectively. A *sam* is the breathe-in point in a *tāl* cycle.
- *Khalī*, meaning ‘empty’ is another kind of the accented point that is on *mātrā* 9 in Figure 1.2. A *khalī* is the breathe-out point in a *tāl* cycle.

Tabla acts as a rhythmic accompaniment and a timekeeper in Hindustani music performances. Apart from this, tabla may also feature as the lead instrument in a tabla solo performance. A difference should be made between *tāl* (the rhythmic framework in Hindustani music) as accompaniment and tabla solo performance [28]. A tabla solo is one where the entire attention is set on the tabla player, which is usually accompanied by a melodic instrument playing a repetitive phrase, having the role of timekeeper. The solo performance is performed in a particular *tāl*. To showcase the nuances of the *tāl* as well as the skill of the percussionist with the tabla, Hindustani music performances feature tabla solos. A tabla solo is intricate and elaborate, with a variety of pre-composed forms used for developing further elaborations. There are specific principles that govern these elaborations [10, p. 42]. Musical forms of tabla such as the *thēkā*, *kāyadā*, *palaṭā*, *rēlā*, *pēškār* and *gaṭ* are a part of the solo performance and have different functional and aesthetic roles in a solo performance.

Tabla in Hindustani music has tradition of stylistic schools called *gharānās*. The term *gharānā* is derived from the word ‘ghar’ which literally means ‘home’. It is used to describe different traditions in music, dance or other art forms established by one artist and his descendants. The *bōls* have freedom in verbal expression and due to different geographical regions, *gharānās* or individual differences, these *bōls* have alternations and permutations of their names [4, p. 58].

The repertoires of major gharānās or schools of tabla differ in aspects such as the use of specific bōls, the dynamics of strokes, ornamentation and rhythmical phrases [4, p. 60]. But there are also many similarities due to the fact that same forms and same standard phrases reappear across these repertoires [10, p. 52]. This enables us to create a library of standard phrases or patterns across compositions of different gharānās. We thus hypothesize that we can discover these phrases across compositions of different gharānās.

1.3 Motivation and Hypothesis

Over the past couple of decades MIR community has made significant advancements in the automatic description of music. However the main focus of the research in MIR has been centered around Western popular music. The technologies developed for this type of music type do not always respond well to the multicultural reality of the diverse world of musics [39, 11]. Methodologies developed are not always directly applicable to the other rich music traditions, such as Indian art music, Makam music in Turkey or Chinese Jingju music. Recently, there has been a lot of research done for description of music specific to these cultures. There has also been some research work reported on melodic description in case of Indian art music [14, 12, 13]. A substantial amount of research has been done for tāl tracking [17, 44] and automatic transcription [1, 24, 43] in case of Indian art of percussions. As we will see in section 2.2, there has been a lot of work for pattern search/discovery type of problems in case of percussions in the Western music. To the best of our knowledge, any work related to pattern search/discovery has yet not been attempted for percussions in case of Indian art music. Automatic discovery of patterns is a relevant Music Information Retrieval (MIR) task. It has applications in enriched and informed music listening and appreciation for listeners, in music training, and in aiding musicologists working on different music cultures.

We use the onomatopoeic oral mnemonic syllables to represent, transcribe and search for patterns in audio recordings of tabla solos. This type of approach has already been used in case of Beijing Opera by Srinivasamurthy et al. [43]. What makes the problem even interesting in our case is:

- The syllables in oral syllabic system, though defined, varies from one school to the other and there is no exhaustive list of syllables. So, it may take some effort to map all the syllables to a unique set of syllables characterized by their timbres.
- As opposed to the case of Beijing opera, neither there is an exhaustive

list of predefined percussion patterns nor there is a proper definition of a percussion pattern.

In this thesis, we propose the hypothesis that the onomatopoeic syllable representation of the tabla bōls can be used to represent and discover the percussion patterns from tabla solo recordings. Our main goals can be summarized as:

- Devise an approach for automatic discovery of percussion patterns from a sizable dataset of tabla solo recordings.
- Evaluate the proposed approach in a comprehensive manner and explain the results.
- Propose further extensions the the current work.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Based on our motivation discussed in the previous section (section 1.3), we use the work done in automatic transcription for percussion instruments in Indian art music as our starting ground and use an approximate string search method to search for percussion patterns. We further hypothesize to aid the approximate string search method with the timbral similarity of the bōls. We hence review the literature which deals with the following three problems:

1. Syllable level transcription of the percussion instruments from the audio
2. Pattern searching techniques incorporated in music information retrieval community
3. Techniques for measuring timbral similarity

For the purpose of syllable level transcription we have reviewed a lot of literature from other syllable based percussion instruments as the studies performed for tabla are limited in number. These instruments include mridangam from Carnatic music, percussion instruments used in Beijing Opera and drum-kit used in the Western music.

2.1 Stroke Level Transcription

The earliest of the scientific attempts in studying of the Indian percussion instruments was performed by C. V. Raman [37]. He studied the harmonic nature of tabla and mridangam. Though tabla and mridangam differ in many ways, their similar anatomy allows to define their five major modes. These modes have been demonstrated with the help of sand figures over the membrane, when they

are excited [37]. This study was important in studying the harmonic nature of these instruments.

More recent research work for these instruments concentrate on the transcription at stroke level. Most of the transcription methods rely on the *segment* and *recognize* type of techniques where:

1. The onset of strokes are detected using a novelty detection methods.
2. The recognition of the strokes are performed with different methods.

For onset detection, in case of mridangam, Anantapadmanabhan et al.[1] use the peaks from the activation matrix computed for the different modes that has been mentioned in the work by C. V. Raman [37]. Onset detection carried out using the group delay algorithms have also been reported [24, 40, 23]. The early research in transcription of tabla strokes by Gillet[9] and Chordia[7] perform an onset detection by using the envelope in the time domain.

Contrary to above approaches there are techniques that perform the transcription without onset detection as the first step. Such kind of approaches have been reported for transcription of mridangam strokes [24]. Here, the experiment is based on *flat-start embedded re-estimation hidden Markov Model*. The accuracy of transcription in this case has been reported to be 59.6%. This is quite poor with respect to the performance where an onset-detection is performed (73.36%). Similar technique have been reported for the transcription of the percussion patterns in Beijing Opera [43]. However, their work is concentrated more on the pattern level than an individual stroke level. They used transcription as an intermediate step for the pattern search. It is important to mention here that Paulus et al. [33] tried to transcribe the drums (unpitched percussion instruments) in polyphonic music using hidden Markov models and without performing a separate detection step. They managed to get the maximum f-measure of 81.5% through one of the methods. This method is dedicated to show that such a solution is possible. We cannot compare this result to that of the case of mridangam [24] because firstly, mridangam strokes are studied including their tonic nature, as they form an essential component of the strokes while in case of drums, the tonic components are completely ignored. Also, Paulus aimed to transcribe individual drums (bass, snare, hi-hat) and not overall timbres due to combinations, and no reference to syllabic percussion was made.

In case of segment and recognize type of approaches, the second step of actual recognition of the syllable, a variety of methods have been put into use. The methods vary both in features being used and the machine learning technique

put into use. Gillet [9] uses mean, variance and relative weight of four frequency peaks as the feature vector, each feature modeled by a single mixture Gaussian. Hidden Markov Models are used to parameterize the shape of the frequency spectrum. Classification was done using naive Bayes, 5-nn or by kernel density estimation. Chordia[7] further extended the work by Gillet[9]. He used temporal features like temporal centroid, attack time and zero-crossing and spectral features like spectral centroid, skewness, kurtosis and thirteen mfccs (including the energy). These are reduced using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Using these features, four different classification techniques are used. These are multivariate Gaussian, feed-forward neural network, probabilistic neural network and tree classifiers. The performance, as compared to the work by Gillet [9], saw an improvement when no language model was being used. This method can be thought of to be better as it uses much larger and diverse database as compared to one used by Gillet[9]. Kuriakose et al.[24] and Anantapadmanabhan et al.[1] use hidden Markov models to model the strokes. The difference lies in the use of features. While Anantapadmanabhan et al.[1] uses the activation related to different modes of mridangam mentioned in the work by C. V. Raman [37], Kuriakose et al.[24] uses the first 13 (including energy) mfcc features including their delta and accelerations (a total of 39) as a feature vector. In the work by Anantapadmanabhan et al.[1], an accuracy upto $\approx 88.40\%$ is reported. The dataset used for this study are all studio recordings. Kuriakose et al. [24] reported results on a much larger and varied dataset is used which gives an accuracy of $\approx 96\%$ on studio recordings and of $\approx 76\%$ on concert recordings. Apart from the features in use, the major reason for the improvement in the performance can, also, be attributed to the use of language model, learned by the HMMs, in correcting the errors. Considering the technique used by Kuriakose et al. [24] and its evident superior performance than the other listed methods, we use a similar approach for the purpose of automatic transcription in our case.

2.2 Pattern Search

Music similarity measurement is important for an automated analysis and detection of musically *similar* fragments. The similarity of the fragments can be defined in various many ways pitch, duration, loudness, timbre, and so on [25]. For percussion instruments, a lot of research has been done to study the problem of discovery of percussion patterns especially in case of drums. Nakano et al. [29] explored drum pattern retrieval using vocal percussion, using an HMM based approach. They used onomatopoeia as the internal representation for

drum patterns with a focus on retrieving known fixed sequences from a library of drum patterns with snare and bass drums. Kapur et al. [22] explored query by BeatBoxing, aiming to map the BeatBoxing sounds into the corresponding drum sounds. A distinction to be noted here is that in vocal percussion systems such as BeatBoxing, the vocalization from the music itself, and not a means of transmission as in the case of instruments with oral syllabic traditions [43]. An interesting fact that has been demonstrated in most of the studies related to transcription is that many of them draw similarity from Natural Language Processing(NLP). This hypothesis been exclusively demonstrated by Mauch and Dixon [27], where they present a quantitative bottom-up approach to the study of rhythm that relies upon well-understood statistical methods of NLP. In our case as well, Tabla solos are built hierarchically using short phrases, and hence some bōl tend to follow a bōl more often than others. In such a scenario, a language model can improve transcription. Srinivasamurthy et al. [43], Kuriakose et al. [24] and Chordia [7] have demonstrated the use of language models to assist the hidden Markov Models in correction of the transcription. Another work in this line is a novel approach of the transcription of individual drums by classifying bar-level drum patterns have been demonstrated by Dixon et al. [47]. One important advantage of this method above the other earlier methods for drum transcription is that, it is also able to model the instruments that have long decays which were a challenge in the frame level based methods. Even if the pattern is classified incorrectly, the individual drum events are classified correctly in some cases. In this case, the evaluation of the classification can actually be taken to the stroke level by computing the similarity between the pattern classes. So, instead of proposing a class for a query pattern, we can actually come up with a regression type of metric.

The most relevant work related to what we want to attempt in this thesis is by Srinivasamurthy et al.[43]. Their approach is to first transcribe the individual strokes from the audio and then classify the transcribed syllable sequences as one of the percussion patterns in a pre-defined library of patterns using various edit distance based methods. As mentioned in the paper, they picked up the case of Beijing opera because it has:

- Well defined oral syllabic system
- Limited set of percussion patterns

Apart from the technique mentioned above, there have been several attempts to deal with search in symbolic representation [49], including dynamic time warping (DTW), longest common subsequence (LCS)-based methods and align-

ment [15, 45, 46]. The DTW algorithm ‘warps’ two sequences non-linearly in the time dimension to evaluate the similarity value, and is suitable for audio or speech comparison [21, 48]. The problem with DTW is that it is not suitable for matching a shorter music segment against a much longer one. To make it work as a search algorithm for long recording against small phrases, we need to divide the longer recordings into smaller chunks. Dividing the large recordings into a smaller chunks is an additional overhead and requires a pre-knowledge of the boundaries of a segment. This in our case is even more difficult as we do not have theoretically well defined boundaries for a segment (percussion pattern). The LCS method evaluates the similarity between two sequences by counting the number of matched symbols without considering the local correlation between the matched subsequence (common subsequence) and each of the two sequences. As a result, the LCS method does not characterize the local information such as gaps or mismatched symbols of the common sequence. Most LCS-based techniques are associated with a penalty function to overcome the problem of global alignment, to become so called local alignment matching [25]. A generalized and novel approach of music matching based on symbolic music representation, which also addresses the problem of local alignment, was proposed by Lin et al. [25]. Here, they describe a method of Rough Longest Common Subsequence (RLCS). Dutta et al. [8] and Ishwar et al. [20] have demonstrated the use of RLCS for motif spotting in *alapanas*¹ of Carnatic music. Since, we are dealing with problem of discovery of percussion patterns from recordings of tabla solos, we will need to deal with the problem of local alignment to search for multiple instances of a percussion pattern in a single recording.

Since we propose to use the RLCS for pattern search, we now explain the different steps involved in RLCS. The RLCS as defined by Lin et al. [25] has three major steps:

- **RLCS:** Computation of the Rough Longest Common Subsequence matrix (a variant of LCS) and tracing back to get the subsequence matches.
- **Width Matrices:** Computation of the width matrices which gives the values of the width of the matched subsequences.
- **Score:** The *RLCS* and the *Width* matrices are then used to compute the final scores of the matches subsequences.

For string based-methods, a music segment (be it a melody or a percussion pattern) is represented by a string or sequence of entries, where each entry

¹An unmetred melodic improvisation usually performed at the beginning of a performance.

specifies the features of one music entry (corresponding to one note or syllable). We now explain each step in detail.

Longest Common Subsequence

Let $X = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m \rangle$ be a sequence or a string of m characters. Then a subsequence must be of the form $X' = \langle x_{i_1}, x_{i_2}, \dots, x_{i_k} \rangle, 1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq m$; while a substring must be of the form $X'' = \langle x_j, x_{j+1}, \dots, x_{j+d} \rangle, 1 \leq j \leq j+d \leq m$. Therefore, any subsequence of X'' must also be a subsequence of X .

In the longest common subsequence (LCS) problem, we are given two sequences and wish to find a maximum-length common subsequence of them. This problem can be efficiently solved using the concept of dynamic programming. LCS has been widely adopted for music matching [25]. However, its value is not enough to reflect the degree of similarity or matching of two sequences. For sequence $X = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m \rangle$, the substring as $X[i, j] = \langle x_i, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_j \rangle$ and the i^{th} prefix as $X_i = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i \rangle$ for $0 \leq i \leq j \leq m$.

Given two sequences $X = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m \rangle$ and $Y = \langle y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n \rangle$ called the reference and query, respectively. The length of the LCS of the prefixes X_i and Y_j can be evaluated by the following recurrence relation:

$$c[i, j] = \begin{cases} 0 & i \cdot j = 0, \\ c[i-1, j-1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } x_i = y_j, \\ \max(c[i, j-1], c[i-1, j]) & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } x_i \neq y_j \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

$c[m, n]$ (from equation 2.1) contains the length of the LCS of X and Y . However, this value is alone not enough for reflecting how good the matching of two sequences is. One should take care of how densely the LCS is distributed over X and Y as well. To do this, the widths of the substrings containing the LCS of X and Y are calculated, called the width-across-reference (WAR) and the width-across-query (WAQ), respectively. A smaller value of WAR/WAQ indicates a denser distribution of the LCS over the reference/query [25].

The values of the WAR and WAQ can be calculated by the recurrence relations given in equations 2.2 and 2.3, respectively, where $w^R[i, j] = \text{WAR}(X_i, Y_j)$ and $w^Q[i, j] = \text{WAQ}(X_i, Y_j)$.

$$w^R[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0, \\ w^R[i-1, j-1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i = y_j, \\ w^R[i-1, j] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] \geq c[i, j-1], \\ & w^R[i-1, j] > 0, \\ 0 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] \geq c[i, j-1], \\ & w^R[i-1, j] = 0, \\ w^R[i, j-1] & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] < c[i, j-1]. \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.2)$$

$$w^Q[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0, \\ w^Q[i-1, j-1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i = y_j, \\ w^Q[i-1, j] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] \geq c[i, j-1], \\ & w^Q[i-1, j] > 0, \\ 0 & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] \geq c[i, j-1], \\ & w^Q[i-1, j] = 0, \\ w^Q[i, j-1] & i \cdot j > 0, x_i \neq y_j, c[i-1, j] < c[i, j-1]. \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.3)$$

With the three matrices c, w^R, w^Q , it is fairly possible to search for the best match of the query prefix Y_j against the reference X_i . The terms $\frac{c[i, j]}{w^R[i, j]}$ and $\frac{c[i, j]}{w^Q[i, j]}$ represent the density of the LCS in X_i and Y_j . The score of the match can then be defined as the product of the weighted average of these two measures and the ratio of the length of the LCS to that of the query, as given in equation 2.4, where β is a weighting parameter and ρ is a required matched rate on the entire query sequence. It is obvious that $0 \leq s[i, j] \leq 1$ and indicates an exact match when $s[i, j] = 1$ [25].

$$s[i, j] = \begin{cases} (\beta \cdot c[i, j]/w^R[i, j] + (1 - \beta) \cdot c[i, j]/w^Q) \cdot (c[i, j]/n) & ; \text{if } c[i, j] \geq \rho n \\ 0 & ; \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

The above metrics allow us to handle the errors of insertions and deletion in case of an automatic transcription. But, this still does not handle the substitution errors.

RLCS for Music Matching

To allow a slight variance from the exact symbol/entry match (representing substitution during automatic transcription in our case), a rough match between

them is preferred. An entry X_i in reference and an entry Y_j in query are said to be matched if $d(X_i, Y_j) \leq T_d$, where $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the distance metric between the symbols/entries and T_d is the threshold distance for which two symbols/entries are said to be matched. Also, now we now compute the matrix c in equation 2.1 by incorporating the rough match as follows:

$$c_r[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0, \\ c_r[i - 1, j - 1] + (1 - d(x_i, y_j)/T_d) & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } d(x_i, y_j) < T_d, \\ \max(c_r[i, j - 1], c_r[i - 1, j]) & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.5)$$

In equation 2.5 we see that a particular pair of symbol/entry is considered to be in the subsequence when the distance between them is below a threshold (as mentioned in previous paragraph). Also, the match is incremented by a normalized similarity score $1 - d(x_i, y_j)/T_d$ between the pair of symbol/entry [25]. By doing this, we take care of the rough match (substitutions in our case) with a score dependent on the extent of match. That is, smaller the distance, greater is the increment. The width matrices are similarly modified as shown below:

$$w_r^R[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0; \\ w_r^R[i - 1, j - 1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) < T_d; \\ w_r^R[i - 1, j] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ & c_r[i - 1, j] \geq c_r[i, j - 1], \\ & w_r^R[i - 1, j] > 0; \\ 0 & i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ & c_r[i - 1, j] \geq c_r[i, j - 1], \\ & w_r^R[i - 1, j] = 0; \\ w_r^R[i, j - 1] & i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ & c_r[i - 1, j] < c_r[i, j - 1]. \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.6)$$

$$w_r^Q[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0; \\ w_r^Q[i-1, j-1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) < T_d; \\ w_r^Q[i-1, j] + 1 & \begin{array}{l} i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ c_r[i-1, j] \geq c_r[i, j-1], \\ w_r^Q[i-1, j] > 0; \end{array} \\ 0 & \begin{array}{l} i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ c_r[i-1, j] \geq c_r[i, j-1], \\ w_r^Q[i-1, j] = 0; \end{array} \\ w_r^Q[i, j-1] & \begin{array}{l} i \cdot j > 0, d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d, \\ c_r[i-1, j] < c_r[i, j-1]. \end{array} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

$$s_r[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} (\beta \cdot c_r[i, j]/w_r^R[i, j] + (1 - \beta) \cdot c_r[i, j]/w_r^Q) \cdot (c_r[i, j]/n) & ; \text{if } c_r[i, j] \geq \rho n \\ 0 & ; \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right. \quad (2.8)$$

Using the equations 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7 we derive the final score matrix with reference to equation 2.4 as shown in equation 2.8. Dutta et al. [8] propose a slight modification to the computation of these metrics by mentioning that $c_r[i, j]$ takes care of the rough matches length. If we consider the term $\frac{c_r[i, j]}{n}$ in equation 2.8, we see that this does not actually considers the fraction of the matched query. Since, we have already taken care of the rough match length densities in the terms involving w_r^R and w_r^Q in equation 2.8, to take care of the fraction of the query matches, Dutta et al. [8] propose a new metric called the *actual length of the RLCS* denoted by c^a as shown in equation 2.9.

$$c_r^a[i, j] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0 & i \cdot j = 0, \\ c_r^a[i-1, j-1] + 1 & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } d(x_i, y_j) < T_d, \\ \max(c_r^a[i, j-1], c_r^a[i-1, j]) & i \cdot j > 0 \text{ and } d(x_i, y_j) \geq T_d. \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.9)$$

Dutta et al. [8] also proposed changes to the width matrices w^R and w^Q but these changes do not actually represent the width of the matched subsequence. So for our purpose, we will use equations 2.3 and 2.2 as width matrices. Our approach and further modifications have been explained in section 3.6.

2.3 Timbral Similarity

There has been a lot of research work done on the concept of timbral similarity in audio and music domain. Logan and Salomon [26] propose an approach to

cluster songs based on their timbral quality. They divide a song into small audio frames (small enough to capture the instantaneous timbre). After obtaining a sequence of transformed frames into a groups which are similar. The number of clusters can be chosen with K-means clustering method where the number of clusters are fixed for each song. In their work, Logan and Salomon [26] modeled each song using 16 clusters. This set of clusters forms the signature for the each song. For each song, the Earth Mover’s Distance [38] is then computed. They demonstrate the results in cases when the relevance is defined by same artist, same album and same genre. They also measured the robustness of their method to simple corruption of audio signals. For 20 songs judged by two users, on average 2.5 out of top 5 matched songs were judged similar. Whereas, in a random playlist generator, this score was 0.2. In an alternate way, the number of clusters can depend on the song as demonstrated by Pelleg and Moore [35]. Aucouturier and Pachet [2] used the measure based on Gaussian model of MFCCs. They initialize the GMM parameters by k-means clustering and train the model with the classic E-M algorithm [5]. They claim that it is 1,000 times more efficient to store the GMM models than the MFCC features. They used different methods to measure the distance between the GMM models of two songs.

- *Likelihood*: Once can match one song (A) against the timbre model of another song (B), by computing the “probability of the data given the model”, i.e. computing the probability that the MFCCs of song A be generated by the model of B. They claim that this is the most precise and logical way to compute a distance, but it requires to have access to the MFCC features of all the songs, but as mentioned earlier, storing them can be a costly affair.
- *Sampling*: In case we have large datasets or there is no access to the features of the dataset, we can use the models directly. While it is easy to compute a distance between two Gaussian distributions, for instance the classical Kullback-Leibler (divergence) distance [5], it is a trickier problem to evaluate a distance between two sets of Gaussian distributions, like in case of GMMs. The method used here is to generate samples from one GMM and to compute the likelihood of the samples given the other GMM. This corresponds to roughly re-creating a song from the timbral model, and applying the likelihood method defined above to this newly created song and the other song’s model.

As a benchmark, they evaluated their system by testing same songs with different audio encodings, different radio broadcasting and found them to be closely matched. Further, they evaluated their methodology for predicting songs with same artists/genres. For objective evaluation, they conducted a quantitative study of the correlation between timbres and artists/genres similarity using the 17,075 songs and their respective meta-data in the Cuidado database [31]. Mentioning the futility of evaluating the predictions using the textual meta data since two songs of the same artist or same genre do not necessarily have close timbres, they conducted a limited subjective evaluation. As opposed to the method for subjective evaluation conducted by Pelleg and Moore [35], where they generated a playlist of different lengths for 20 query songs and then asked the subjects to mark the songs in the playlist as ‘similar’ or ‘non-similar’ to the query song, while Aucouturier and Pachet [2] presented a target song **S** and test songs **A** and **B**. The user was then asked to tell which song of the two test songs is closer to the target song **S**. They pick up one of the two test songs from the top 20 neighbors as computed by their approach. In my view, this is not a correct approach for subjective evaluation because here we are comparing two songs against the target song which is not a case real situations and might contribute to misleading results.

The problem of computing of the Kullback-Leibler distance between two GMMs was more comprehensively addressed by Hershey and Olsen [16]. They introduced two new methods of variational approximation and the variational upper bound and compared them to the other methods viz. Monte Carlo sampling, Unscented Transformation, Gaussian Approximations, Product of Gaussian Approximations and the Matched Bound Approximation [16]. The KL divergence is used in many aspects of speech and image recognition, determining if two acoustic models are similar [30] and measuring how confusable two words or HMMs are [36, 41, 19]. Since, in automatic transcription we propose to draw similarity from speech recognition models, using KL divergence as a metric to compute similarity between the syllable models seems like an obvious step for our case.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter we describe the step-by-step approach towards our devised methods for discovery of percussion patterns from the solo recordings. The block diagram in Figure 3.1 shows our overall approach. We formulate the problem of discovery of percussion patterns in tabla solo recordings. We present a general framework for the task, while outlining some of the challenges. The approach we explore is to use syllables to define, transcribe, and eventually search for percussion patterns. We build a fixed set of syllabic query patterns. Given an audio recording, we obtain a time-aligned syllabic transcription using syllable level timbral models. For each of the query patterns in the set, we then do an approximate search on the output transcription to obtain the locations of the patterns in the audio recording. We describe each of the steps in detail.

We first compile a comprehensive set of syllables in tabla. However, the syllables vary marginally within and across different gharānās and several bōls can represent the same stroke on the tabla. To address this issue, we grouped the full set of 41 syllables into timbrally similar groups resulting into a reduced set

Sym.	bōls	Sym.	bōls
DA	D, DA, DAA	NA	N, NA, TAA, TU
KI	KA, KAT, KE, KI, KII	DIN	DI, DIN, DING, KAR, GHEN
GE	GA, GHE, GE, GHI, GI	KDA	KDA, KRA, KRI, KRU
TA	TA, TI, RA	TIT	CHAP, TIT

Table 3.1: The bōls used in tabla, their grouping, and the symbol we use for the syllable group. The symbols **DHA**, **DHE**, **DHET**, **DHI**, **DHIN**, **RE**, **TE**, **TII**, **TIN**, **TRA** have a one to one mapping with a syllable of the same name and hence not shown in the table.

of 18 syllable groups as shown in Table 3.1. Though each syllable on its own has a functional role, this timbral grouping is presumed to be sufficient for discovery of percussion patterns. We limit ourselves to the reduced set of syllable groups and use them to represent patterns. For convenience, when it is clear from the context, we call the syllable groups as just syllables and denote them by the symbols in Table 3.1. Further, we use bōls and syllables interchangeably. Let the set of syllables be denoted as $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_M\}$, $M = 18$.

A percussion pattern is not well defined and varied definitions can exist. Here, we use a simplistic definition of a pattern, as a sequence of syllables. A pattern is defined as $P_k = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{L_k}]$ where $s_k \in \mathcal{S}$ and L_k is the length of P_k . Though, for defining patterns, it is important to consider the relative and absolute durations of the constituent syllables, as well as the metrical position of the pattern in the tāl, we use a simple definition and leave a more comprehensive definition for future work. We take a data driven approach to build a set of K query patterns, $\mathcal{P} = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_K\}$.

Given an audio recording $x[n]$, it is first transcribed into a sequence of time-aligned syllables, $T_x = [(t_1, s_1), (t_2, s_2), \dots, (t_{L_x}, s_{L_x})]$, where t_i is the onset time of syllable s_i . The task of syllabic transcription has a significant analogy to connected word speech recognition using word models. Syllables are analogous to words and a percussion pattern to a sentence - a sequence of words. Finally, given a query pattern P_k of length L_k , we search for the pattern in the output syllabic transcription T_x , to retrieve the subsequences $p_k^{(n)}$ in T_x ($n = 1, \dots, N_k$) that match the query, where N_k is the number of retrieved matches for P_k . We use $p_k^{(n)}$ and the corresponding onset times from T_x to extract audio segments corresponding to the retrieved syllabic patterns. Syllabic transcription is often not exact and it can have common transcription errors such as insertions, substitutions and deletions, to handle which we need an approximate search algorithm.

In the following sections, we first describe the dataset that has been used for the experiments. Following that, we describe our approach for the transcription of syllables from the audio. After that, we describe the approach through which we arrive at a set of patterns that are then used query patterns for our search algorithm. We, then, describe the method for the pattern search in the symbolic domain using the approximate string search methods of Rough Longest Common Subsequence and propose some variants of it to suit to our purpose. We now describe the dataset we have put into use.

Figure 3.1: The block diagram of the approach

3.1 Dataset

To evaluate our approach to percussion pattern discovery, we need a parallel corpus with time-aligned scores and audio recordings. We prepared a dataset of 38 solo compositions. The dataset is a parallel corpus with time-aligned scores and audio recordings. The purpose of having this dataset was, both, building isolated stroke timbre models for the purpose of transcription and a comprehensive evaluation of the complete approach. The audio for these compositions were obtained from the instructional video DVD *Shades Of Tabla* by Pandit Arvind Mulgaonkar¹. The DVD has 120 compositions which are distributed amongst 8 tracks. The first 6 tracks showcase the different gharānās of tabla (Ajrada, Benaras, Dilli, Lucknow, Punjab and Farukhabad). We chose 38 representative compositions spanning all the gharānās. The booklet accompanying the DVD provides a syllabic transcription for each composition. Along with the transcribed score, we have some meta-data associated with each composition. The meta-data includes the gharānā, serial number of compositions in the DVD, form of composition, its jāti, the tāl (which is always teental in our case) and the name of the composer, if available. We used Tesseract [42]², an open

¹<https://musicbrainz.org/release/220c5efc-2350-43dd-95c6-4870dc6851f5>

²<https://github.com/tesseract-ocr>

source Optical Character Recognizer (OCR) engine to convert printed scores and meta-data to a machine readable format. The text obtained from OCR was manually verified and corrected for errors, adding the the vibhāgs (sections) of the tāl to the syllabic transcription.

We extracted audio from the DVD video and segmented the audio for each composition from the full audio recording. The audio recordings are stereo, sampled at 44.1 kHz and have a soft harmonium accompaniment. A time aligned syllabic transcription for each score and audio file pair was obtained using a spectral flux based onset detector [3] followed by manual correction by the authors. The dataset contains about 17 minutes of audio with over 8200 syllables. The annotation of the solo recording which includes marking the boundaries of the compositions from the full length recordings, and marking of the onsets of the syllables was done using Sonic-Visualizer³. The dataset will be available for research purposes through a central online repository⁴.

3.2 Preliminary Experiments

Before attempting to automatically transcribe the score from the audio for the purpose of pattern search, we first attempt to look into the feasibility of detecting patterns using the simple syllable modeling approach. For this purpose, we try to model each syllable with the help of Gaussian Mixture Models. The stereo audio is converted to mono, since there is no additional information in stereo channels. We use the MFCC features to model the timbre of the syllables. We use the HTK toolkit to obtain the MFCC features [50]. To capture the temporal dynamics of syllables, we add the velocity and the acceleration coefficients of the MFCC. The 13 dimensional MFCC features (including the 0th coefficient) are computed from the audio with a frame size of 23.2 ms and a shift of 5.8 ms. We also explore the use of energy (as measured by the 0th MFCC coefficient) in transcription performance. Hence we have two sets of features, MFCC_0_D_A, the 39 dimensional feature including the 0th, delta and double-delta coefficients, and MFCC_D_A, the 36 dimensional vector without the 0th coefficient.

We use the Gaussian Mixture Models to model each syllable. We experiment with different number of components for the Gaussian Mixture Models. We first obtain the bag of features for each syllable in the syllable group. Each feature in bag of features is a feature vector of the MFCC features as described

³<http://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>

⁴<http://compmusic.upf.edu/tabla-solo-dataset>

Figure 3.2: Distribution of number of frames amongst different syllables

above. Since, the duration of a *bōl* instance is larger than that of a frame, there are multiple frames from a single *bōl* instance contributing towards the bag of features. In our dataset, the occurrence of number of instances of different *bōl*s is different and hence the number of frames in each bag of features vary over a wide range. This has been shown in Figure 3.2. After getting the bag of features we then train a GMM model for each *bōl* using the module Scikit-learn [34] in python which provides implementation for training and testing of GMM models. We experimented with different number of components of GMM to model a *bōl*.

We show results for 3-component GMM as the result did not vary a lot on changing the number of components. Also, our motive for demonstrating this approach is to show why is this approach is not working and why we need better methods. We now describe the approach. Once we have GMM models for each syllable, we compute the log likelihoods given by each *bōl* model for feature vector of each frame in the test solo recording. We plotted the result of this likelihoods using some compositions from the training set itself. The output of one of those has been shown in Figure 3.3. We can consider the output of log likelihoods by each of the *bōl* GMM model for a frame as an output feature vector and compute a self-similarity matrix. The self-similarity matrix for the log likelihood values shown in Figure 3.3 has been shown in Figure 3.4. We can clearly see that the self similarity matrix is not very informative. The reason for the poor performance here is that we are not actually modeling the

Figure 3.3: Log likelihoods of all the frames (x-axis) as given by models (3-component GMM) of bōl (y-axis) for a composition.

timbre of the bōls here. As the timbre is dependent on the evolution of a sound over time, we need to consider that as well. With the approach that we just demonstrated, we do not consider evolution of the bōls over time but say that each frame associated with a particular bōl is one of its characteristics and then try to model all the characteristics of the bōls. Since the frames have very small time duration as compared to the entire bōl, there is a lot of overlap between the characteristics of all the bōls and hence, this kind of modeling does not really work in our case.

To model the evolution of bōls over time we use the hidden Markov models. We draw similarity from the speech technologies and use the onomatopoeic nature of the bōls to transcribe them in a similar way the words are transcribed in a speech. We then use the RLCS approach of rough string match on the automatically transcribed score to search for query patterns.

3.3 Transcription

The bōl of tabla may be pronounced with a different vowel or consonant depending on the context, without altering the drum stroke [6]. Furthermore, the bol and drum strokes vary across different gharana, making the task of transcription of tabla solos challenging. To model the timbral dynamics of syllables, we build an HMM for each syllable (analogous to a word-HMM). We use these

Figure 3.4: Self similarity matrix for the Figure 3.3 with the log likelihoods acting as a feature vector.

HMMs along with a language model to transcribe an input audio solo recording into a sequence of syllables.

The stereo audio is converted to mono, since there is no additional information in stereo channels. We use the MFCC features to model the timbre of the syllables. To capture the temporal dynamics of syllables, we add the velocity and the acceleration coefficients of the MFCC. The 13 dimensional MFCC features (including the 0th coefficient) are computed from the audio with a frame size of 23.2 ms and a shift of 5.8 ms. We also explore the use of energy (as measured by the 0th MFCC coefficient) in transcription performance. Hence we have two sets of features, *mfccoda*, the 39 dimensional feature including the 0th, delta and double-delta coefficients, and *mfccda*, the 36 dimensional vector without the 0th coefficient.

Using the features extracted from training audio recordings, we model each syllable S_m using a 7-state left-to-right HMM $\{\lambda_m\}$, $1 \leq m \leq M(= 18)$, including an entry and an exit non-emitting states. The emission density of each emitting state is modeled with a three component Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to capture the timbral variability in syllables. We experimented with higher number of components in the GMMs, but with little performance improvement. We use the time aligned syllabic transcriptions and the audio recordings in the parallel corpus to do an isolated HMM training for each syllable. We then use these HMMs further in an embedded model Baum-Welch re-estimation to get the final syllable HMMs.

Tabla solos are built hierarchically using short phrases, and hence some bol

ID	Pattern	L	Count
1	DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA	16	47
2	TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA	16	10
3	TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI	8	61
4	TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI	6	214
5	TA, TA, KI, TA	4	379
6	KI, TA, TA, KI	4	450
7	TA, TA, KI, NA	4	167
8	DHA, GE, TA, TA	4	97

Table 3.2: Query Patterns, their ID (k), length (L) and the number of instances in the dataset (Total instances: 1425)

tend to follow a bol more often than others. In such a scenario, a language model can improve transcription. In addition to a flat language model with uniform unigram and transition probabilities, i.e. $p(s_1 = S_m) = 1/M$ and $p(s_{i+1} = S_m/s_i = S_n) = 1/M$, with $1 \leq m, n \leq M$ and i being the sequence index, we explore the use of a bigram language model learned from data.

For testing, we treat the feature sequence extracted from test audio file to have been generated from a first order time-homogeneous discrete Markov chain, which can consist of any finite length sequence of syllables. From the extracted feature sequence, we use the HMMs $\{\lambda_m\}$ and a syllable network constructed from the language model to do a Viterbi (forced) alignment, which aims to provide the best sequence of syllables and their onsets T_x . All the transcription experiments were done using the HMM Toolkit (HTK) [50].

3.4 Query Patterns

We take a data driven approach to create a set of query patterns of length $L = 4, 6, 8, 16$. These lengths were chosen based on the structure of teental for different *lay* (tempo classes) [4, p. 126]. Using the simple definition of a pattern as a sequence of syllables, we use the scores of the compositions to generate all the L length patterns that occur in the score collection. We then sort them by the number of occurrences to get an ordered set of patterns for each stated length. We then manually choose the most musically representative patterns to form a set of query patterns. Table 3.2 shows the chosen patterns, their

length and their count in the dataset, leading to a total of 1425 instances. We also want a diverse collection of patterns to see if the algorithms extend and generalize. Hence we choose patterns that have a varied set of syllables, and have different timbral characteristics like syllables with harmonic nature (**DHA**), syllables played with a flam (**DHE, RE**) and syllables having bass (**GE**).

We have chosen patterns of different lengths to observe the change in performance of the search algorithm with the length of the patterns. The shorter patterns ($L = 4$) are the most frequent and form the building blocks for larger patterns. Because of less number of syllables, we hypothesize them to be more prone to errors as compared to the larger patterns. Also, since we are using mapped syllables for getting the set of patterns, the count for a particular pattern is contributed by different patterns with mapped syllables. This would rather help us in finding timbrally similar patterns.

3.5 Error Analysis on Transcribed Data

Before trying search for patterns in the automatically transcribed compositions, it is important to analyze the transcribed data for errors and see what kind of errors are actually present. We first analyze the length of the syllable sequences in the transcribed data which lie in the same time boundary as the query patterns in the ground truth score. For this purpose, we first extracted all the instances of the query patterns in the ground truth with their time boundaries in the form of onsets of the boundary syllables. We then searched for the closest onsets in the automatically transcribed sequence of syllables to these boundary syllables for the query patterns in the ground truth. We used a binary search approach for this purpose. We plotted the histogram showing the number of syllable sequences with different lengths. Figure 3.5 shows the plot for this for P_1 in Table 3.2. We see a lot of distribution of the patterns over the different lengths. The maximum frequency is with the length 16 which is seen in the graph. There are substantial amount of patterns with length 15 and 17 as well. So, surely there are insertions and deletions during transcription. But, the insertions and deletions are not a lot in number. This is evident from the fact that in a pattern of length 16 has only one or two insertions across the entire length. This can also be seen in case of P_5 in Table 3.2 where the maximum number of syllable sequences are of length 4. We definitely see a lot of deletions and few insertions here but again they are quite less in number as compared to the syllable sequences of length 4.

It is interesting to analyze the different groups of patterns that the automatic

Figure 3.5: Distribution of length of true positive and false negative syllable sequences for P_1 (Table 3.2)

Figure 3.6: Distribution of length of true positive and false negative syllable sequences for P_5 in Table 3.2

transcription result into. For this purpose, for each query pattern, we grouped the transcribed sequence of syllables within the same time boundaries as the ground truth. For P_1 in Table 3.2, there are 47 types of patterns which mean that on 2 instances are exactly the same. Some of these have been mentioned in Table 3.3. Out of the 47 different groups, we chose these three groups because the errors that occur towards the start of the sequence are the most common amongst all the sequence groups. We clearly see that in the second syllable sequence, **DHE** is being confused with **RE**. Also in the third sequence group **DHE** is being confused with **GE**. The reason for this is when all these syllables are played very fast, they may not be played in the ideal way and may have either the *dāyān* or the *bāyān* more pronounced which might cause the confusion as we see here. In the second syllable sequence, *dāyān* is more pronounced and hence the model detects **RE**. Contrary to this, in the third sequence, we see that **GE** has been detected instead of **DHE**. Here, the *bāyān* is more pronounced than the *dāyān*. Ideally, this should have been handled by the language model used in the transcription models but since the examples of the syllables **DHE** and **RE** are too less in our dataset, so it could not learn the relationship properly. Also, since we are only learning binary language models it could not learn the relationship with further syllables. Learning an n -gram language model with n as 3, 4 or other higher values might help in improving the transcription. Other errors that occur are the insertion of an extra **DHE**, **RE** after the first two **DHE**, **RE**. Other syllables like **TA** have been confused by **DA**.

If we look at the P_5 , total 397 (Table 3.2) have been transcribed into 167 groups of syllable sequence with highest occurrence (78) of the correct pattern **TA**, **TA**, **KI**, **TA** (Table 3.4). The syllable sequence with highest count

Syllable Sequence	L	Count
DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, KI, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI	15	2
RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TRA, KI, NA, DA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA	16	1
GE, RE, DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, KI, GE, KI, TA, TA, KI	16	1

Table 3.3: Some of the syllable sequences in the transcribed data at positions where P_1 (3.2) occur in ground truth (L: Length of the syllable sequence)

Syllable Sequence	L	Count
TA, TA, KI, TA	4	78
KI, TA, TA, KI	4	26
NA, KI, TA, TA	4	19
TA, TA, KI	3	14

Table 3.4: Some of the syllable sequences in the transcribed data at positions where P_5 (3.2) occur in ground truth (L: Length of the syllable sequence)

after TA, TA, KI, TA is KI, TA, TA, KI. The reason for this confusion is mostly because both TA, TA, KI, TA and KI, TA, TA, KI have all the bōls which are closed and when played fast can be confused with each other. Also, as we have seen that the most occurring pattern in the dataset is P_6 (Table 3.2). Since, we have trained the HMM syllable models using language models, the maximum occurring pattern (KI, TA, TA, KI as shown in Table 3.2) gets an advantage in case of a confusion. The syllable sequence with the next highest number of occurrence is NA, KI, TA, TA (Table 3.4). The reason that we get a NA in the beginning is that a lot of times TA, TA, KI, TA is played just after a ringing syllable. Due to its prominence, the starting syllable is confused at many places resulting into a substitution by NA. Lastly, we talk about the syllable sequence TA, TA, KI. This is the result of the deletion of the last syllable TA. The reason for this is that when the pattern P_5 is played very fast all the onsets might not be detected.

Analyzing the P_6 (Table 3.2), a total of 379 pattern instances have been transcribed into 178 groups of syllable sequences. Again, the highest occurrence is that of the query pattern itself i.e. KI, TA, TA, KI (Table 3.5); a total of 65 instances. The next highest number of instances are of the the syllable sequence KI, TA, TA (34 instances). The reason here for confusion is the

Syllable Sequence	L	Count
KI, TA, TA, KI	4	65
KI, TA, TA	3	34
RE, KI, TA, TA	4	15
TA, TA, KI, TA	4	15

Table 3.5: Some of the syllable sequences in the transcribed data at positions where P_6 (3.2) occur in ground truth (L: Length of the syllable sequence)

same as for the syllable sequence TA, TA, KI in case the query pattern is TA, TA, KI, TA. When the pattern is played at high speed, the onsets might not get detected. Next most frequent syllable sequence is RE, KI, TA, TA with a count of 15 instances. Here, the pattern is being confused with a part of pattern P_1 in Table 3.2. Next most frequent syllable sequence that is confused with P_6 is TA, TA, KI, TA. The reason here is same as discussed before where TA, TA, KI, TA was confused by KI, TA, TA, KI and here the case is just the opposite.

Summarizing the above discussion, from Figures 3.5 and 3.6, we can see that for both patterns P_1 and P_5 the length of the modes of the automatically transcribed syllable sequences have lengths equal to the respective query pattern. This shows us that the majority of errors are the substitution errors. Also, in both the figures we see that the instances of transcribed syllable sequences with length less than that of the query pattern are more as compared to the sequences with length more than the query pattern. Hence, from this initial analysis we can say that the instances of the deletion errors are more than that of the insertion errors.

In the next section, we will the explain the method we propose to deal with the errors that arise during the automatic transcription. Talking about the RLCS formulation as modified from the one described in section 2.2 specific to our case, we will specifically describe the technique of timbral similarity we adopt to deal with the substitution errors.

3.6 Pattern Search on Symbolic Data

Figure 3.7: Block Diagram for the RLCS approach

Figure 3.7 shows the overall RLCS approach for the pattern search. The automatically transcribed output syllable sequence T_x is used to search for the query patterns. Transcription is often inaccurate in both the sequence of syllables and in the exact onset times of the transcribed syllables. We need to handle both these errors in a pattern search task from audio. We primarily focus on the errors in syllabic transcription. We use the syllable boundaries output by the Viterbi algorithm, without any additional post processing. We can improve the output syllable boundaries using an onset detector [3], but we leave this task to future work.

There are three main kinds of errors in the automatically transcribed syllable sequence: Insertions (I), Deletions (D), and substitutions (B). Further, the query pattern is to be searched in the whole transcribed composition, where several instances of the query can occur. Rough Longest Common Subsequence (RLCS) method is a suitable choice for such a case. RLCS is a subsequence search method that searches for roughly matched subsequences while retaining the local similarity [25]. We can make further enhancements to RLCS to handle the I, D and B errors in transcription.

We use a modified version of the RLCS approach as proposed by Lin et al. [25] with changes proposed by Dutta et al. [8] to handle substitution errors. We propose a further enhancement to handle insertions and deletions, and explore its use in the current task. We first present a general form of RLCS and

then propose different variants of the algorithm.

Given a query pattern P_k of length L_k and a reference sequence (transcribed syllable sequence) T_x of length L_x , RLCS uses a dynamic programming approach to compute a score matrix (of size $L_x \times L_k$) between the reference and the query with a rough length of match. We can use a threshold on the score matrix to obtain the instances of the query occurring in the reference. We can then use the syllable boundaries in the output transcription and retrieve the audio segment corresponding to the match.

For the ease of notation, we index the transcribed syllable sequence T_x with i and the query syllable sequence P_k with j . We compute the rough and actual length of the subsequence matches similar to the way computed by Dutta et al. [8]. At every position (i, j) , a syllable is included into the matched subsequence if $d(s_i, s_j) < \delta$, where $d(s_i, s_j)$ is the timbral distance between the syllables at positions i and j in the transcription and query, respectively. δ is the threshold distance below which two syllables are said to be equivalent. The matrices of rough length \mathbf{C} and the actual length \mathbf{C}^a of match are updated as,

$$\mathbf{C}(i, j) = \mathbf{C}(i-1, j-1) + (1 - d(s_i, s_j)) \cdot \mathbb{1}_d \quad (3.1)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^a(i, j) = \mathbf{C}^a(i-1, j-1) + \mathbb{1}_d \quad (3.2)$$

where, $\mathbb{1}_d$ is an indicator function that takes a value of 1 if $d(s_i, s_j) < \delta$, else 0. The matrix \mathbf{C} thus contains the length of rough matches ending at all combinations of the syllable positions in reference and the query. The rough length and an appropriate distance measure handles the *substitution* errors during transcription. To apply a penalty for *insertion* and *deletion* errors, we compute a “density” of match using two measures called the Width Across Reference (WAR) and Width Across Query (WAQ), respectively. The WAR (\mathbf{R}) and WAQ (\mathbf{Q}) matrices are initialized to $\mathbf{R}_{i,j} = \mathbf{Q}_{i,j} = 0$ when $i, j = 0$, and propagated as,

$$\mathbf{R}_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_{i-1,j-1} + 1 & d(s_i, s_j) < \delta \\ \mathbf{R}_{i-1,j} + 1 & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} \geq \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1}, \mathbf{R}_{i-1,j} > 0 \\ 0 & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} \geq \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1}, \mathbf{R}_{i-1,j} = 0 \\ \mathbf{R}_{i,j-1} & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} < \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{Q}_{i-1,j-1} + 1 & d(s_i, s_j) < \delta \\ \mathbf{Q}_{i-1,j} & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} \geq \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1} \\ \mathbf{Q}_{i,j-1} + 1 & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} < \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1}, \mathbf{Q}_{i,j-1} > 0 \\ 0 & d(s_i, s_j) \geq \delta, \mathbf{C}_{i-1,j} < \mathbf{C}_{i,j-1}, \mathbf{Q}_{i,j-1} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

$\mathbf{R}_{i,j}$ is the length of substring containing the subsequence match ending at the i^{th} and the j^{th} position of the reference and the query, respectively. $\mathbf{Q}_{i,j}$ represents a similar measure in the query. When incremented, $\mathbf{R}_{i,j}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{i,j}$ are incremented by 1 similar to the way formulated by Lin et al. [25]. At the same time, the increment is done based on the conditions formulated by Dutta et al. [8].

Using the rough length of match (\mathbf{C}), actual length of match (\mathbf{C}^a) and width measures (\mathbf{R} and \mathbf{Q}) we compute a score matrix σ that incorporates penalties for substitutions, insertions, deletions, and additionally, the fraction of the query matched.

$$\sigma_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \left[\beta \cdot f\left(\frac{\mathbf{C}_{i,j}}{\mathbf{R}_{i,j}}\right) + (1 - \beta) \cdot f\left(\frac{\mathbf{C}_{i,j}}{\mathbf{Q}_{i,j}}\right) \right] \cdot \frac{\mathbf{C}(i,j)}{L_k} & \text{if } \frac{\mathbf{C}^a(i,j)}{L_k} \geq \rho \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\sigma_{i,j}$ is the score for the match ending at the i^{th} and the j^{th} position of the reference and the query, respectively. f is a warping function for the rough match length densities $\frac{\mathbf{C}_{i,j}}{\mathbf{R}_{i,j}}$ in the reference and $\frac{\mathbf{C}_{i,j}}{\mathbf{Q}_{i,j}}$ in the query. The parameter β controls their weights in the convex combination for score computation. The term $\frac{\mathbf{C}^a(i,j)}{L_k}$ is the fraction of the query length matched and is used for thresholding the minimum fraction of the query to be matched.

Starting with all combinations of i and j as the end points of the match in the reference and the query, respectively, we perform a traceback to get the starting points of the match. RLCS algorithm outputs a match when the score is more than a score threshold ψ . However, with a simple score thresholding, we get multiple overlapping matches, from which we select the match with the highest score. If the scores of multiple overlapping matches are equal, we select the ones that have the lowest width (WAR). This way, we obtain a match that has the highest score density. We use these non-overlapping matches and the corresponding syllable boundaries to retrieve the audio patterns.

3.6.1 Variants of RLCS

The generalized RLCS provides a framework for subsequence search. The parameters ρ , β , ψ and δ can be varied to make the algorithm more sensitive to different kinds of transcription errors. The variants we consider here use different distance measures $d(s_i, s_j)$ in Equation 3.1 to handle substitutions and different functions $f(\cdot)$ in Equation 3.5 to handle insertions and deletions in a non-linear way. We explore these variants for the current task and evaluate their performance.

Figure 3.8: Plot of Equation 3.6 for different values of κ

In a default RLCS configuration (RLCS_0), we only consider exact syllable matches. We use a binary distance metric based on the syllable label, i.e. $d(s_i, s_j) = 0$ if $s_i = s_j$, 1 otherwise, and set $\delta = 1$. Further, an identity warping function, $f(y) = y$ is used. This means that, this variant of RLCS only handles the insertion and deletion errors.

The rough length match densities can be transformed using a non-linear warping function to penalize low density values more than the higher ones, leading to another variant of RLCS (RLCS_κ). We explore warping functions of the form,

$$f(y) = \frac{e^{\kappa y} - 1}{e^{\kappa} - 1} \quad (3.6)$$

where $\kappa > 0$ is a parameter to control warping, larger values of κ lead to more deviation from an identity transformation. RLCS_0 is a limiting case of RLCS_κ when $\kappa \rightarrow 0$. The plots for the value of function mentioned in Equation 3.6 has been shown in Figure 3.8. The figure shows the plot of the function for different values of κ for the input range $[0, 1]$.

We hypothesize that the substitution errors in transcription are due to the confusion between timbrally similar syllables. A timbral similarity (distance) measure between the syllables can thus be used to make an RLCS algorithm insensitive to specific kinds of substitution errors. In essence, we want to disregard and give a greater allowance for substitutions between timbrally similar syllables during RLCS matching. Computing timbral similarity is a wide area

of research and has many different proposed methods [32] (Section 2.3). We call this variant of RLCS as RLCS_δ and experiment with different thresholds δ .

3.6.2 Timbral Distance

Modeling signatures for songs on the basis of timbre have already been dealt in handful of works [26, 38, 35, 2, 5]. We choose to address the problem of timbral similarity by modeling them using the Gaussian Mixture models (GMMs) and then computing the Kullback-Leibler divergence between them. The KL divergence is used in many aspects of speech and image recognition, determining if two acoustic models are similar [30, 16]. Since, there is no closed form solutions for computing KL divergence between two GMMs, Hershey and Olsen proposed approximations of the same [16]. We demonstrate the use of two such methods. We first use the method defined as Monte Carlo Sampling and Gaussian Approximations [16]. Hershey and Olsen claim that the only method that can really estimate $D(f||g)$ which is the KL divergence between two probability density functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$, and defined as:

$$D(f||g) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \int f(x) \log \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} dx \quad (3.7)$$

Equation 3.7, also known as *relative entropy*, is commonly used in statistics as a measure of similarity between two density distributions. The divergence satisfies three properties, referred to as divergence properties.

1. Self similarity: $D(f||f) = 0$
2. Self identification: $D(f||g) = 0$ only if $f = g$.
3. Positivity: $D(f||g) \geq 0 \forall f, g$.

Figure 3.9: Plot of the syllable similarity measured between GMM models (4 component each) of the syllables. The distance is measured as an approximation of KL divergence using Monte Carlo sampling.

For Monte Carlo sampling, the idea is to draw a sample x_i from the pdf f such that $E_f[\log f(x_i)/g(x_i)] = D(f||g)$. For our purpose, we found the distance between models of two syllables (as mentioned in Section 3.2), say bol_1 and bol_2 by generating n random samples from one one model and then calculating the log likelihood of these samples from the other. The distance is then computed by taking the the difference between the mean of the likelihoods by the two models. The distance between all permutations of the syllables (we say permutation because the KL divergence is not a symmetric metric) is then scaled in the range $[0, 1]$. Figure 3.9, shows the plot of similarity between the syllables of which were modeled using 4 component GMMs and the distance between the permutation of syllables was computed as an approximation of KL divergence using the Monte Carlo sampling.

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

4.1 Transcription

The transcription results shown in Table 4.1 are the mean values in a leave-one-out cross validation over the dataset. We experimented with the two different MFCC features (MFCC_D_A and MFCC_0_D_A) and two language models (a flat model and a bigram learnt from data). Overall, we see a best Accuracy of 53.13%, which justifies the use of a robust approximate string search algorithm for pattern retrieval. The use of a bigram language model learned from data improves the transcription performance. We see that the Accuracy measure is lower than the Correctness measure, which shows that there are a significant number of insertion errors in transcription. We use the output transcriptions from the best performing combination (MFCC_0_D_A and a bigram language model) to report the performance of the RLCS variants.

	Feature	Corr.	Accu.
Flat lan- guage model	MFCC_D_A	64.07	45.01
	MFCC_0_D_A	64.26	49.27
Bigram lan- guage model	MFCC_D_A	65.53	49.97
	MFCC_0_D_A	66.23	53.13

Table 4.1: Transcription results showing the Correctness (Corr.) and Accuracy (Accu.) measures (in percentage) for different features and language models. In each column, the values in bold are statistically equivalent to the best result (in a paired-sample t-test at 5% significance levels).

Figure 4.1: Self similarity matrix in score space for the ground truth score of composition no. 3 in the dataset

Figure 4.2: Self similarity matrix in score space for the automatically transcribed score of composition no. 3 in the dataset

Once the automatically transcribed scores (the result from MFCC_0_D_A and a bigram language model) are obtained, we try to visualize it by computing a self similarity matrix in the syllable space. Here, we define the similarity as 1 if two syllables are same and 0 otherwise. We then plot this similarity matrix. We try the result for one of the simplest compositions (in terms of length and

Variant	Parameter	Precision	Recall	F-measure
Baseline	-	0.479	0.254	0.332
RLCS ₀	$\delta = 1$	0.384	0.395	0.389
RLCS _{δ}	$\delta = 0.3$	0.102	0.581	0.173
RLCS _{δ}	$\delta = 0.6$	0.095	0.584	0.163
RLCS _{δ}	$\delta = 0.9$	0.095	0.584	0.163
RLCS _{κ}	$\kappa = 1$	0.412	0.350	0.378
RLCS _{κ}	$\kappa = 4$	0.473	0.268	0.342
RLCS _{κ}	$\kappa = 7$	0.482	0.259	0.336
RLCS _{κ}	$\kappa = 9$	0.481	0.258	0.335

Table 4.2: Performance of different RLCS variants using the best performing parameter settings for RLCS₀ ($\rho = 0.875$, $\beta = 0.76$ and $\psi = 0.6$).

tempo class of the composition) in our dataset. We choose composition number 3 which is from Dilli gharānā. For comparison, first, we compute the self similarity matrix from the ground truth score in our dataset Figure 4.1. Similarly, we compute the self similarity matrix for the automatically transcribed score Figure 4.2. If we compare the two, we can see that the one with the automatically transcribed score has some discrepancies with respect to the one with the ground truth. This is expected because of the standard errors of the automatic transcription (insertion, deletion and substitution). Although, this does not give us the clear idea about the accuracy of the automatic transcription, we can validate for the fact that similar timbres are transcribed as same syllable.

4.2 Pattern Search

In this section, we elaborate the pattern search experiments that we performed with different variants that we proposed in section 3.6. We begin by describing the setting of the baseline (reported in Precision, Recall and f-Measure). After setting the baseline, we report the results of RLCS₀, RLCS _{δ} and RLCS _{κ} . Finally, we analyze the results for different patterns in our set of query patterns for the case of RLCS₀.

Setting the Baseline

To form a baseline for string search performance with the output transcriptions, we used an exact string search algorithm and report its performance in Table 4.2 (shown as Baseline). We see that the baseline has a precision that is similar to

Figure 4.3: Plot for True Positive rate and False Positive rate for varying β with $\rho = 0.875$ and $\psi = 0.6$

transcription performance, but a very poor recall leading to a poor F-measure. This can be attributed to the mentioned transcription errors viz. Insertion, Deletion and Substitutions. It would also be interesting to see as to which of these errors are more prominent. We already seen an earlier analysis of errors in the automatically transcribed score as mentioned in Section 3.5. The interesting thing would be to see if our earlier observations comply with the current observations or not.

Variants RLCS₀

This variant of RLCS deals only with the insertion and deletion errors. We performed a grid search over the values of β , ρ and ψ with RLCS₀. β and ψ are varied in the range 0 to 1. To ensure that the minimum length of the pattern matched is at least 2, we varied ρ between $1/\min(L_k)$ and 1. This also helped us in saving some computation time. With this grid search, we established the optimum parameter settings for RLCS₀. $\rho = 0.875$, $\beta = 0.76$ and $\psi = 0.6$ retrieved us with the best f-Measure and we use these parameters to evaluate our other variants of the RLCS.

The effect of β which is the convex sum parameter that weighs the contribution of the rough match length density of reference and query towards the final score has been shown in Figure 4.3. In the figure, we see that as the value of β increases, both the true positive rate and the false positive rate decreases. With

Figure 4.4: Distribution of length of true positive and false positive syllable sequences for P_1 in Table 3.2

Figure 4.5: Distribution of length of true positive and false positive syllable sequences for P_5 in Table 3.2

increasing β , to the reference length ratio, allowing more insertions. Since, with increasing β , we get a poor true positive rate, we conclude that during transcription, the insertions contribute to a majority of transcription errors. In Figure 4.3, we have plotted β varying from 0.41 to 0.96. The reason for this being that the values of β in range $0.0 < \beta < 0.41$ cluster around a single point near 0.41. The reason that they cluster is that when the value of β is in the range $0.0 < \beta < 0.41$, more weight is on the deletions and since the score performance does not change, it is again evident that insertion errors are more prominent than the deletion errors (Figure 4.4 for P_1 in Table 3.2 and Figure 4.5 for P_5 in Table 3.2). These observations are, however, contradictory to the ones made in Section 3.5 (showing true positives and false negatives) where we claimed that the deletion errors are the more prominent than the insertion errors. The reason for this is this that in the true positive cases that are missed have large number of substitutions and hence have a low score in case of $RLCS_0$. As we will see later in case of $RLCS_\delta$, the recall rate improves with a good amount when we introduce the concept of timbral similarity between the syllables. It also has restrictions which have also been discussed.

The best average F-measure over all the query patterns in an experiment using $RLCS_0$ is reported in Table 4.2. We see that $RLCS_0$ improves the recall, but with a lower precision and an improved F-measure, showing that the flexibility in approximate matching provided by RLCS comes at the cost of additional false positives. The values of ρ , β and ψ that give the best F-measure are then fixed for all subsequent experiments to compare the performance of the proposed RLCS variants.

It is interesting to analyze the results of different patterns and explain the

S. No.	Pattern	P	R	Fm
1	DHE, RE, DHE, RE, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, NA	0.69	0.57	0.62
2	TA, TA, KI, TA	0.10	0.50	0.17
3	TA, KI, TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI	0.23	0.47	0.37
4	TA, TA, KI, TA, TA, KI	0.55	0.52	0.54
5	TA, TA, KI, TA	0.45	0.40	0.42
6	KI, TA, TA, KI	0.35	0.26	0.30
7	TA, TA, KI, NA	0.28	0.45	0.34
8	DHA, GE, TA, TA	0.36	0.40	0.38

Table 4.3: Pattern specific result for RLCS₀ ($\rho = 0.875$, $\beta = 0.76$ and $\psi = 0.6$)

reason behind these results. Table 4.3 shows the results in Precision, Recall and F-measure for different patterns in our query set. There are two aspects to each query pattern which might govern the performance of a particular pattern. First, the repetitiveness within a pattern and second, having or not having well defined boundaries of a pattern. The repetitiveness means that there are sub-patterns of the original patterns which are repeated within. This might result in ambiguity for the search algorithm. Another aspect is the boundary of a query pattern. If the boundary is not well-defined, it means that there is repetition of a sub-pattern within throughout the length which creates an ambiguity in the starting and ending. The important point to note here is that, according to our definition, for a pattern to have well-defined/not well-defined boundaries, it necessarily needs to have repetitions within. P_1 in Table 4.3 has well defined boundaries with few repetitions within. Whereas, P_2 , P_3 , P_4 , P_5 and P_6 are patterns of different lengths that do not have well defined boundaries. P_5 and P_6 are exceptions in the sense that they do not have repetitions within. These being very small, their not well-defined boundaries arise even without having repetitions within. P_5 and P_6 are basically the smaller repetitive patterns forming the patterns P_2 , P_3 and P_4 .

Due to a long length of 16 bōls and well defined boundaries, P_1 in Table 4.3 has the highest precision and recall amongst all the query patterns. P_2 , also with length 16, has the poorest performance amongst all the query patterns. The reason for this is that P_2 does not have well defined boundaries with lot of repetitions of much smaller pattern. Going forward to P_3 , we see remarkable improvement of performance over P_2 . The reason behind this is that the start-

ing and ending of P_3 are much more distinguishable as compared to P_2 in the sense that P_2 starts and ends with the same pattern P_5 . Comparing P_5 and P_6 , we see that P_6 is more symmetric and also due to highest number of training examples in the dataset for the purpose of modeling the syllable HMM models, the transcription might be a little biased towards this pattern and hence generating a higher number of false positives as compared to true positives. Hence, resulting to poorer precision. Poorest precision of P_7 amongst all the length 4 patterns tell us that the syllable **NA** might be a highly confused syllable during transcription. This can be due to the fact that it is a ringing syllable and if the bass of a ringing syllable is missed, it can easily be confused with P_7 .

The results with other variants of RLCS are also reported in Table 4.2. The results from $RLCS_\delta$ show that the use of a timbral syllable distance measure with higher threshold δ further improves the recall, but with a much lower precision and F-measure. Here, for $RLCS_\delta$ we show the results for the similarity matrix as shown in Figure 3.9 (KL divergence between 4 component GMM models of the syllables using Monte Carlo sampling). Although we find matches that have substitution errors using the distance measure, we retrieve additional matches that do not have substitution errors contributing to additional false positives. On the contrary, using a non-linear warping function $f(\cdot)$ in $RLCS_\kappa$ improves the precision with a higher value of κ as the penalties on matches with higher number of insertions and deletions is high and they are left out, leading to good precision, but at the cost of recall. We observe that both the above mentioned variants improve either precision or recall at the cost of the other measure. They need further exploration with better timbral similarity measures to be combined in an effective way to improve the search performance.

Chapter 5

Summary and Future Work

In the last chapter of the dissertation we, first provide the summary of the work done. Following that we list down the main conclusions that we draw from the work done. This is followed by listing down the open issues and the possibilities of the future work. Lastly we list down the main contributions of this dissertation.

5.1 Summary of work

We addressed the unexplored problem of a discovering syllabic percussion patterns in Tabla solo recordings. The presented formulation used a parallel corpus of audio recordings and syllabic scores to create a set of query patterns, that were searched in an automatically transcribed (into syllables) piece of audio.

We started with a brief introduction of the instrument tabla mentioning its relevance in Hindustani music. We described various parts of the instrument. We then introduced the concept of onomatopoeic syllables in the domain of tabla. Further we described the concept of rhythm in Hindustani music explaining its essential features. We mention the features that vary amongst different gharānās of the tabla. We also discuss the invariability of some of the standard percussion patterns amongst different gharānās and thus hypothesize on automatic discovery of percussion patterns.

We formulate the problem by saying that the discovery of percussion patterns can be done by, first, statistically retrieving the musically relevant syllable sequences from the ground truth score. Thus, creating a set of query patterns. This is followed by automatic transcription of the given solo recording into a syllable sequence followed by running an approximate string search algorithm on it to search for the query patterns. We reviewed the work dealing with the

problem of automatic transcription for percussion instruments. Specifically, we emphasized on the work dealing with the automatic transcription in case of instruments having the concept of onomatopoeic syllables, thus drawing similarity from the speech technologies. We further reviewed the literature related to pattern search specific to domain of music technology. We describe various methods that have been put into use for pattern search in symbolic domain. We, specifically, describe the Rough Longest Common Subsequence and hypothesize to use it for dealing with the transcription errors in our case. To handle the substitution errors during automatic transcription, we reviewed some literature on timbral similarity.

We used a simplistic definition of a pattern and statistically discovered the query patterns of different lengths in the ground truth transcription. We used HMM models for modeling the syllables and further used the models to automatically transcribe syllable sequence from the solo recordings. We explored RLCS based subsequence search algorithm. We proposed different variants of the RLCS and experimented with the same.

5.2 Conclusions

Even though discovery of percussion patterns in Indian art music can be seen as one of the most important problems in the MIR community having many application, it has not received the deserved attention. Past work with respect to percussion instruments in Indian art music has been mostly concentrated on the automatic transcription of onomatopoeic syllables.

We try to push the boundary further to a higher level of abstraction i.e. the percussion patterns. We try to search for patterns in the automatically transcribed scores from the tabla solo recordings. To overcome the errors of the automatic transcription, we use an approximate subsequence match method of RLCS. Compared to a baseline, we showed that the use of approximate string search algorithms improved the recall at the cost of precision. Additionally, proposed variants improved either the precision or recall, but do not provide a significant improvement in the F-measure over the basic RLCS.

5.3 Open issues and Future work

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work on percussion patterns in case of tabla and hence it has a lot of limitations. The major aim of this work was to prove that in spite of the errors in the state of the art transcription procedures,

we can discover the percussion patterns from the tabla solo recordings by the help of an appropriate approximate substring search method. Although we have been able to show that this approach works to some extent, there are some issues that need to be addresses in the future work.

- **Limited Dataset:** In this thesis, we have experimented only on dataset coming from a single source. Even more the tonic of the compositions in the dataset are same. It would be interesting to see how well the method of automatic transcription scales up to different tonics in case of tabla. All the compositions in the dataset used have been played by a single artist in a studio like setup. It would be interesting to see the degree of robustness of the RLCS method of approximate substring match for recordings by other artists in other setups (like live recordings).
- **Syllable Timbral Similarity:** To deal with the substitution errors, we have used the concept of timbral similarity between the syllables. In the present work we have limited ourselves to measuring the timbral similarity by measuring the distances between the GMM models of the syllables. The limitation here is that in doing so we have not considered the temporal evolution of the syllables as opposed to the approach we have taken in case of transcription where we have modeled the temporal evolution of the syllables using the HMM models. Since we are measuring the timbral distance in one way and modeling the syllables for transcription in other way, one of the concerns could be if were are comparing apples and oranges. It might be for the same reason that we do not get very good results with the used distance metric. It would surely be interesting to use a metric based on the distances between the HMM models of the syllables that have been trained for the purpose of transcription.
- **Perceptual Studies:** The evaluation that we have performed in this work is very objective in the sense that it rates a retrieved pattern as correct if the query pattern occurs at exactly the same place in the ground truth. This could lead to categorizing the retrieved patterns as a false positive which might actually be perceptually similar to the query pattern. To counter this error, it would be interesting to do a subjective evaluation of the retrieved patterns with real people ranking the retrieved pattens. Although we have already grouped the syllables based on their timbre, we cannot ensure that we will be able to find perceptually similar patterns since a pattern is a group of syllables and the way a group of syllables evolve also contributes to its timbre. So, conducting a perceptual test

with people would help us in evaluating our approach in a much more comprehensive way.

- **Assisting Pattern Search with Rhythmic Information:** In the current work the definition of the percussion patterns that we have used is very simplistic. We do not consider the rhythmic information contained inside the solo recordings that comply with the *tāl* framework. Percussion patterns perceptually tend to start and end complying with the *tāl* framework. Hence the rhythmic information could help us to get rid of many false positives. There has been quite a lot of research that has taken place to detect the important places in a *tāl* cycle (especially the *sam*) [18, 44]. Using this information, we can definitely expect improvements in the current performance.

5.4 Main Contributions

In this section we list down the important contributions that have been made through the course of this dissertation.

- A pioneering work in attempting the discovery of percussion patterns from the tabla solo recordings.
- Scientific background and review of relevant work and techniques pertaining to automatic transcription of onomatopoeic syllables, pattern search specific to domain of music, and timbral similarity.
- Compilation of a dataset¹ comprising of 38 solo compositions. The dataset is a parallel corpus of audio along with stroke level annotated scores with the time stamps of the strokes (syllables).
- Code: An implementation of the Rough Longest Common Subsequence in python which can easily reproduce the stated results. The code is available through a Github repository².
- Relevant Publications:
S. Gupta, A. Srinivasamurthy, M. Kumar, H.A. Murthy, X. Serra. Discovery of Syllabic Percussion Patterns in Tabla Solo Recordings. In International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR-2015), 2015

¹<http://compmusic.upf.edu/tabla-solo-dataset>

²<http://compmusic.upf.edu/ismir-2015-tabla>

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Hindustani Music

baddhi Leather strings that keeps the membrane in place.

bāyān The left drum of a tabla set.

bōl The onomatopoeic syllables.

dāyān The right drum of a tabla set.

gharānā Represents a particular school of tabla.

jāti Jati represents a type of rhythmic pattern.

śīśama Teak wood.

chanti Part of the membrane of the instrument.

gajarā Part of the membrane of the instrument.

gamak Modulation of tonal frequency.

khālī Breathe-out point in a tala cycle type.

lipi Script of writing down something.

mātrā The lowest metrical pulse.

maidān Part of the membrane of the instrument.

MFCC_D_A MFCC features without energy but with delta and double-delta coefficients.

MFCC_0_D_A MFCC features with energy, delta and double-delta coefficients.

purī Membrane of the instrument.

sam The first mātrā of an āvart.

syahi Part of the membrane of the instrument.

tāl The rhythmic framework of Hindustani music.

tabla The primary percussion accompaniment in Hindustani music.

gaṭ A composition type in tabla.

kāyadā A composition type in tabla.

palaṭā A composition type in tabla.

pēškār A composition type in tabla.

rēlā A composition type in tabla.

ṭhēkā The basic bōl pattern associated with a tāl.

tālī Breathe-in point in a tala cycle type.

vibhāg The sections of a tāl.